

Original Research

Comparison of Critical Thinking and Financial Self-Efficacy of Freshman and Senior Accounting Students

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Abstract

This study aimed to analyze critical thinking and financial self-efficacy in accounting freshmen and seniors. The primary goal of this research was to investigate the difference and relationship between critical thinking and financial self-efficacy in freshmen and seniors. Critical thinking was introduced as an important skill enabling students to analyze problems and evaluate results. This skill can help university students perceive financial problems completely and make better decisions on financial management. Two standard scales were used in this study: Facione's California Critical Thinking Skills Test and Lown's Financial Self-Efficacy Scale (FSEF). Initially, the concepts of critical thinking and financial self-efficacy were discussed in a brief introduction. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used in SPSS to analyze data collected from questionnaires. The research sample included 41 freshmen and 52 seniors (n=93). According to the results, accounting seniors had higher levels of critical thinking and financial self-efficacy than accounting freshmen. In conclusion, it is essential to develop critical thinking and financial self-efficacy in accounting freshmen. Their critical thinking and financial self-efficacy can be improved significantly by providing educational programs and teaching financial management skills, which can enhance their capabilities to make financial decisions and manage financial affairs. Therefore, this study can provide useful guidelines for improving critical thinking and financial self-efficacy in students.

Keywords: Accounting students, critical thinking, financial self-efficacy.

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Introduction

The education system of a country plays a key role in training and nurturing human resources in every major, e.g., accounting (Khajavi & Nahas, 2019). Academic accounting programs not only present the concepts and techniques of accounting but also consider forming the personal and social contexts of students (Bowl, 2018). At universities, a preliminary course in accounting can serve as an important determinant of students' decisions on whether to continue studying accounting or to pursue another major (Eikner & Montondon, 2001). This preliminary course is usually presented as a basic course in the accounting curriculum. Many future employers use this course as an index of the ability to organize tasks and achieve success in accounting (Sanders & Willis, 2009). Using the theories and concepts of other majors, e.g., psychology and educational management, can help improve the process of learning accounting (Khajavi & Nahas, 2019). This interdisciplinary approach assists university students to consider accounting problems more comprehensively from a more balanced perspective, thereby having a better perception of those problems. Additionally, students' thoughts and attitudes play a pivotal role in the success of higher education. In other words, their attitudes and beliefs can have direct effects on their learning, thinking, and performance. Thus, their attitudes and beliefs must be considered and modified diligently to improve higher education.

Critical thinking denotes the logical evaluation and detailed analysis of events, claims, and data. This skill helps individuals look at problems logically and impartially, analyze different reasons and arguments, and draw justifiable conclusions about their actions. Critical thinking assists students in several ways, such as perceive basic concepts of the discipline, analyze data, make logical deductions, solve problems, and make better decisions. Therefore, critical thinking is essential to accounting students. This skill helps them be more successful in their education and professional lives (Hurst, 2006). Financial self-efficacy is another variable of academic success.

By definition, financial self-efficacy denotes an individual's belief in his/her own ability to manage and control financial affairs. This belief includes self-confidence in financial planning, budget management, savings, and investment. A high level of financial self-efficacy motivates a person to act more effectively in financial management. Personal financial planning is a tool that helps an individual to set financial goals and make specific plans to achieve those goals. Budgeting, saving, and investment are among the key components of financial planning. Appropriate financial planning can help a person improve his/her financial status and experience a better financial life (Yazdani, 2022). The academic success of accounting students can be affected by different factors and opportunities. For instance, they may face different financial conditions in different academic years, having various opportunities for earning income. These conditions can have many effects on their financial self-efficacy.

The primary mission of universities is to nurture students physically and mentally in the right way (Azizinejad et al, 2014). Therefore, universities need to improve the physical, emotional, and cognitive energies of students to achieve appropriate comprehension and acquire new knowledge (Urmetzer et al, 2020). This study aims to compare accounting freshmen with accounting seniors in terms of critical thinking and financial self-efficacy. Known as a basic skill in higher education, critical thinking helps

students gain correct results through logic. This skill improves the ability to analyze and evaluate claims and reasons logically. Furthermore, financial self-efficacy is considered an important factor that indicates an individual's ability to manage his/her financial affairs and meet his/her financial needs, especially among accounting students. By analyzing differences and variations in critical thinking and financial self-efficacy in academic programs, education officials can offer appropriate plans and actions to enhance of education.

Problem Statement

Among the main concerns of the higher education system in the country, in addition to the transfer of concepts and education, is the ability to use critical thinking skills, problem solving, and scientific and technological literacy. These skills are essential for sustainability and continuous learning. In addition to learning scientific concepts, students need to be able to pay attention to the methods of searching for scientific information, and instead of accumulating information, they need to be able to look at issues in a deep-thinking manner, make decisions, and make judgments about various issues. Therefore, the main goal of any educational system is to educate people with critical, creative, critical thinking and a scientific perspective (Sadooghi Yadgari & Bakshesh, 2023).

Critical thinking helps students solve problems, make decisions and achieve goals. Critical thinking is an active process that leads to successful outcomes. For example, if critical thinking skills are actively used in solving students' problems, it will have an effective and successful result. Critical thinking skills play an important role in many fields of education and learning, especially in the field of cognitive intelligence (Tusankogal, 2018).

One of the main challenges in universities is teaching academic subjects, including accounting. In the 21st century, educating students who are ready to face a dynamic and changing society is a great challenge. Critical thinking as a basic skill is always needed by accounting students and graduates. In this regard, the CPA exam presents questions that require critical thinking. Participants must provide solutions to identified problems with in-depth analysis (Turkzadeh et al., 2023).

On the other hand, according to social cognitive theory, financial self-efficacy can have a significant effect on people's financial behavior. This theory is based on the principle that a person's beliefs and attitudes about the power of predicting and managing financial situations affect their decisions and efforts. When people believe that they have sufficient ability to face financial challenges and obstacles, they have higher financial self-efficacy. This self-confidence can lead to a person's choice of behavior, effort and perseverance in reaching financial goals. With financial self-efficacy, a person may be more inclined to make successful financial decisions and persist in pursuing his goals to the last point (Gilaninia & Montazeri, 2019).

Critical thinking and financial self-efficacy are two important factors that can influence the strength and performance of students in accounting and finance. But the question raised here is whether there is a difference between critical thinking and financial

self-efficacy in first and final year accounting students, or in other words, are the financial abilities and attitudes of these two groups different?

Theoretical foundations

Critical thinking and financial self-efficacy are two key concepts in education; they are essential to university students (Paul & Elder, 2006). The intellectual skills of students constitute an important aspect of higher education. Given sociocultural developments, this problem still draws substantial attention and poses many challenges to the higher education system. If education is not organized carefully and not implemented correctly, society will sustain serious damage. Therefore, university students should be nurtured and directed toward professional careers by considering social needs, developing correct schemes, and making accurate plans (Delavari, 2015).

The main goal of the higher education system is to nurture lifelong learners. However, in the age of information explosion and rapid developments, what is learned now may be changed or replaced in the future. Therefore, higher education systems should not only focus on providing information regarding a specific field of knowledge. They should teach students how to learn and think. In this regard, developing critical thinking is essential for university students. Critical thinking is a skill that assists individuals in the process of active, dynamic learning and turns them into self-managed, self-directed learners. This skill also helps students analyze data logically and present reliably logical results to solve problems. As a result, they can improve critical thinking to recognize and analyze complicated problems, to which they can then respond creatively and innovatively. Ultimately, enhancing critical thinking can prepare university students to encounter future developments and challenges, providing them with the necessary tools for growth in their professional careers (Sriantini et al, 2022).

Facione (2015) is a theorist who divided critical thinking into a metacognitive dimension and an emotional dimension. The metacognitive dimension includes problem-solving, evaluating options, and decision-making. These skills help students analyze problems logically and find the best solutions. The metacognitive dimension also includes inferential skills, analysis, evaluation, induction, and syllogism, helping students reach accurate, logical reasoning.

The emotional dimension of critical thinking includes paying attention to other people's feelings and opinions, evaluating options and values, and being able to perceive and interpret feelings. These skills help students express their opinions and feelings in addition to perceiving others profoundly. Empathizing with others and perceiving their feelings can help students find the best solutions concerning other people's needs and values. In the 20th century, critical thinking was considered a research topic discussed in studies of education and learning. The roots of critical thinking are traced back to Greek philosophers, e.g., Socrates, Plato, and Aristotle. These philosophers defined critical thinking as the process of inquiring about, testing, and thinking about ideas and values. Genuinely, critical thinking denotes the logical evaluation of ideas and values. It is now considered an important topic in learning and education (Javidi Kalateh Jafarabadi & Abdoli, 2010).

Critical thinking is a process whereby individuals can logically analyze and evaluate problems, claims, and reasons. In particular, this type of thinking can bring about the ability to perceive and interpret information. There is no consensus about critical thinking among pundits because it is complicated and conceptual due to its complex subjective process. One reason for the complexity of critical thinking lies in the use of various concepts and models in this process. Moreover, critical thinking requires the ability to analyze data and information qualitatively and quantitatively; this requirement leads to problems in the measurement and description of critical thinking (Athari et al,2011). Additionally, the definition of critical thinking is a factor that results in the lack of consensus among pundits. Every researcher has defined critical thinking based on their personal perceptions and research needs. However, these definitions may vary in different scientific and cultural communities, something which causes inequality in opinions and definitions (Javidi Kalateh Jafarabadi & Abdoli,2010). Generally, it is difficult to measure and describe critical thinking accurately due to its complexity, conceptuality, and diverse definitions. Furthermore, personal habits and cultural differences affect the process of reaching a uniform definition of critical thinking (Bottom of Form).

In general, thinking is considered an important skill in every education system, as it gives a more profound perception of topics and prepares students to solve complex problems and update educational concepts. Critical thinking is a skill that can help students analyze evidence accurately and infer results. Therefore, students will be able to analyze processes and make better decisions. It also helps students improve their creativity and innovation and express their opinions and theories independently. Universities and higher education centers should design their educational programs to help enhance critical thinking in students. For this purpose, they can hold critical thinking classes, present group activities for enhancing critical thinking, and encourage writing activities and analytical discussions. For this purpose, UNESCO has emphasized the importance of teaching critical thinking at universities and higher education centers, where it is considered the primary task (Shakournia & Keikha 2019).

The Bandura social cognitive learning theory in 1986 analyzes human behavior in a threefold communicative structure that includes behavior, environmental variables, and personal factors (e.g., personal cognition). In this structure, an individual affects and is affected by both environment and behavior. Moreover, environmental factors and behavior have reciprocal effects in this relationship. In other words, not only does every factor affect another factor, but it is also affected by that factor. According to Bandura, extrinsic factors and intrinsic factors (e.g., predictions) can affect results and decisions. This theory emphasizes that human behavior is affected simultaneously by environmental factors and personal factors, in which bilateral relationships play key roles (Olson & Ramírez, 2020).

Financial self-efficacy is analyzed through the social cognitive theory, which evaluates the role of cognitive thinking in people's motivation drive and financial behavior(Sandler, 2000). According to this theory, the structure of financial self-efficacy has direct effects on personal choices or tasks and indirect effects on the realization of positive outcomes usually predicted by individuals when financial self-efficacy is related to a specific area. In other words, increasing financial self-efficacy helps a person make better predictions and achieve positive results(Bandura, 2005).

Financial self-efficacy refers to people's belief in their ability to manage financial resources and make the right financial decisions (Payne & Asebedo, 2019). This is a major factor that has substantial effects on students' financial behavior and their prosperity. Studies have shown that university students with high levels of financial self-efficacy are more involved in positive financial behaviors, e.g., budgeting, saving, and making investments. Financial self-confidence allows individuals to better manage their resources and make the right financial decisions that can facilitate their personal development and economic prosperity (Heckman et al, 2014).

Financial self-efficacy makes individuals increase their efforts to achieve financial goals and become stable in the face of problems and obstacles. This finding is backed by the studies indicating that financial self-efficacy has direct effects on the augmentation of people's efforts and diligence to reach their financial goals (Rashidi, 2012). Additionally, financial self-efficacy is not limited only to a person's financial affairs; it can affect other aspects of life. People with high levels of financial self-efficacy tend to show positive behavioral changes in general and experience numerous improvements in life (Ismail et al., 2020). Financial self-efficacy improves the prosperity of students and prepares them to become successful in the future. According to studies, financial self-efficacy plays a pivotal role in forming the financial behaviors of students and developing their prosperity (Sahid, Nuris, & Hussin, 2023).

Therefore, universities and educational institutions need to provide students with resources and support so that they can develop their financial self-efficacy. These resources can include educational courses in financial management, presenting educational information and references concerning financial areas, providing personal financial counseling, and creating practical opportunities for practical experience in financial management. These actions allow students to hone their financial skills, enhance their financial self-confidence to make the right financial decisions, and experience improvement in their financial prosperity. Not only do these measures help students, but they also play a key role in nurturing a generation with high levels of financial management and sustainable economic growth. There is a paucity of research on critical thinking and financial self-efficacy in Iran and other countries. Some relevant studies are reviewed below.

In a study entitled *Analyzing the Relationships of Financial Literacy and Financial Attitude with Financial Self-Efficacy in Accounting Students of Mashhad*, (Nouri, 2021) analyzed the relationships of financial literacy and financial attitude with financial self-efficacy in the accounting students of Mashhad, Razavi Khorasan Province (Iran). They selected 195 accounting students of Mashhad as the research sample. Their research tools included three questionnaires on financial knowledge, financial attitude, and financial self-efficacy. According to their results, financial knowledge and financial attitude had significant relationships with the financial self-efficacy of students. Moreover, there was a difference between female and male students in terms of financial knowledge. These findings indicated that financial knowledge and financial attitude can play key roles in improving the financial self-efficacy of accounting students in Mashhad.

(Mildawani et al, 2022) analyzed the relationship between critical thinking and competitive behavior prediction by drawing a social comparison. The results indicated

that critical thinking failed to predict competitive behavior through a social comparison. In other words, competition is a type of complicated behavior accompanied by cognitive factors, personal traits, and self-adaptive characteristics and cannot be separated from the social context.

(Gilaninia et al, 2020) analyzed the factors affecting financial self-efficacy in accounting students. According to their results, the quality of financial learning and the socioeconomic status of parents had positive significant effects on the financial literacy of accounting students. Furthermore, financial literacy had a positive significant effect on the financial self-efficacy of accounting students and mediated the relationship between the quality of financial learning and financial self-efficacy of accounting students. Furthermore, financial literacy mediated the relationship between the socioeconomic status of parents and the financial self-efficacy of accounting students.

(Herawati et al,2020) analyzed the effects of parents' financial learning quality and their socioeconomic status on the financial self-efficacy of accounting students in Bali, Indonesia, with the mediating role of financial literacy. For this purpose, they employed a quantitative method and the path analysis technique. They also analyzed data through a financial literacy test and questionnaires collected with the purposive random sampling method. According to their results, parents' financial learning quality and their socioeconomic status had direct effects on the financial literacy of students that could directly affect financial self-efficacy. The results also indicated that financial literacy could mediate the relationships of parents' financial learning quality and their socioeconomic status with students' financial self-efficacy.

(Heckman et al,2014) employed the structure proposed by Danes and Haberman (2007) to measure the levels of financial self-efficacy in students. According to their results, there was a positive relationship between students' financial knowledge and their financial self-efficacy.

(Tashi et al, 2012) analyzed the skills of critical thinking in 92 medical students of three different grades. According to the results, students did not have satisfactory scores in those skills; therefore, educational programs should be devised to enhance their skills. There were also low levels of evaluation, analysis, inference, deductive reasoning, and inductive reasoning in all three groups of students, whose mean scores were different in various subsets.

(Rahnamay Roudposhti et al, 2012) evaluated the critical thinking levels of accounting students in studying their specialized texts at the Science and Research Branch of Islamic Azad University. According to the results, students used critical thinking skills slightly in general, and gender had no significant effects on their tendency to critical thinking. Moreover, senior students had higher levels of critical thinking than junior students.

(Sugahara et al,2010) analyzed the level of self-efficacy of Australian students in accounting skills was investigated. The results of this research showed that accounting education programs do not have much effect on improving self-efficacy in accounting skills and only in analytical skills, students' self-efficacy improves. Also, people who

have work experience and English mother tongue have higher self-efficacy in general skills.

Research Hypotheses

H₁: There is a difference between accounting freshmen and accounting seniors in critical thinking.

H₂: There is a difference between accounting freshmen and accounting seniors in financial self-efficacy.

H₃: There is a significant relationship between critical thinking and financial self-efficacy.

Method

In this study, a descriptive method was employed in a casual-comparative research design. The causal-comparative technique determines differences between various groups and their inputs instead of comparing equivalent groups exposed to different research variables. In this study, freshmen and seniors were selected to analyze their differences in critical thinking and financial self-efficacy. The initial method began by describing the status quo and searching in previous events to determine the hypothetical antecedents existing prior to the study. The review of historical background and previous events led to the identification of effective factors in the critical thinking and financial self-efficacy of students. Some solutions were then offered to improve the status quo.

The statistical population included accounting freshmen and seniors at Yazd University. The Accounting Department of Yazd University was selected as the statistical population due to its abundant knowledge of accounting, direct contact with students, and contact with the professional accounting atmosphere. Convenience sampling was employed to select accounting freshmen and seniors in the academic year 2022–2023. In other words, sampling was based on availability and simplicity. The sample included 41 freshmen and 52 seniors (n=93).

The research questionnaire consisted of three sections of items:

A) Social demographics: gender, age, term status: Constituting an important part of the research, these variables help us interpret the results better concerning different characteristics of the statistical population.

B) Critical Thinking Items: The California Critical Thinking Skills Test–Form B (CCTST–B) was employed to evaluate critical thinking in students. Developed in 1997, this questionnaire is known as one of the most practical tools for evaluating critical thinking (Facione et al,1995). It consists of 34 items focused on the five major components of critical thinking: analysis, inference, evaluation, deductive reasoning, and inductive reasoning. The participants are expected to select the best choice. Every correct response has one point. The total score ranges from 0 to 34, and the cutoff point is 17. The scores of different sections of this questionnaire indicate a respondent's strengths and weaknesses in critical thinking. High scores represent high levels of critical thinking,

whereas low scores mean poor performance in this skill. Some changes were made to the contents and items of this questionnaire to adapt to the perception levels of Farsi-speaking students (Asgari & Maleki, 2010).

C) Financial Self-Efficacy Items: Designed to evaluate self-efficacy in financial decisions, Lown's Financial Self-Efficacy Scale (FSEF) (2011) includes the general scale of self-efficacy and the scales of financial behavior, especially financial self-efficacy. The respondents evaluated their financial self-efficacy by using six sentences scored on a Likert scale. The score of each sentence was calculated concerning the summation of scores. In this questionnaire, the scores range from a minimum value of 6 to a maximum value of 30. This questionnaire is known as a reliable tool that can be used for evaluating self-efficacy in financial decisions. It can be employed to evaluate a person's financial self-efficacy. High scores indicate high levels of self-efficacy, whereas low scores represent poor performance in this skill (Khoobani, 2017).

Findings

Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for data analysis. Means, standard deviations, minimum scores, and maximum scores were used in the descriptive section. Descriptive statistics enable researchers to describe different features of data quantitatively. However, inferential statistics help researchers draw generally acceptable conclusions based on the research data. In other words, inferential statistics enable us to make important inferences through data analysis.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1. Descriptive statistics for critical thinking and financial self-efficacy in accounting freshmen and seniors

Variable	Statistical Index	Academic Year	
		Freshman Year	Senior Year
Critical Thinking	Mean	11.51	14.15
	Standard Deviation	0.507	0.491
	Minimum Score	5	7
	Maximum Score	23	21
Financial Self-Efficacy	Mean	20.77	21.20
	Standard Deviation	0.648	0.521
	Minimum Score	12	13
	Maximum Score	30	30

Inferential Statistics

Kolmogorov–Smirnov Test

The Kolmogorov–Smirnov test is employed to check the normality of data, although it considers no specific distribution. It is also used in the analysis of variance to check the normality of data. According to Table 2, the P-value is lower than the confidence level (0.05). Therefore, the data on financial self-efficacy had a normal distribution, whereas

the data on critical thinking did not have a normal distribution. As a result, the mean of financial self-efficacy can be used as a measure of central tendency for relevant data. The Kolmogorov–Smirnov test results can help researchers ensure the accuracy of their results. They can use this test in their future decisions. Table 2. Factors influencing cyber loafing.

Research Hypothesis Findings

In this study, a t-test and an F-test were used for independent groups to analyze the first hypothesis and the second hypothesis. These tests were conducted to compare the two groups in their scores on critical thinking and financial self-efficacy. The analysis of variance should be employed to compare the first two means. Firstly, the variances of the two populations were analyzed. The t-test was then used to analyze the equality of means when the variances were equal. Furthermore, Levene’s test was used in the ANOVA, and there was no need to differentiate data based on the normal distribution (Hafez Nia, 2016).

Additionally, a paired t-test was employed to analyze the third hypothesis addressing the relationship between critical thinking and financial self-efficacy. This test was used to investigate the relationship between the two foregoing variables and analyze their mutual effects. In this section, various tests were employed to analyze research hypotheses and questions.

Table 2. The Kolmogorov–Smirnov Test

Research Index	Sig. Level	Sample Size
Critical Thinking	0.003	93
Self-Efficacy	0.240	93

Hypothesis 1 – There is a difference between accounting freshmen and accounting seniors in critical thinking.

$$H_0: \sigma_1^2 = \sigma_2^2$$

$$H_1: \sigma_1^2 \neq \sigma_2^2$$

Firstly, Levene’s test was used to determine whether the two populations had equal variances. According to the results of Levene’s test, the significance level was 0.214, which was greater than the confidence level (5%). The null hypothesis was confirmed, indicating that the two populations had equal variances.

$$H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$$

$$H_1: \mu_1 \neq \mu_2$$

In the next step, the t-test was used to analyze the hypothesis of the mean. According to the results, the significance level was 0.002, which was smaller than the confidence level (5%). Therefore, the null hypothesis (i.e., there is no significant difference between the two populations in mean) was rejected, and Hypothesis 1 (i.e., there is a significant

difference between accounting freshmen and seniors in critical thinking) was confirmed. According to the mean values, seniors improved critical thinking as opposed to freshmen.

Table 3. Testing Hypothesis 1

Groups	Mean	F-value (Sig.)	t-value (Sig.)
Freshmen	11.83	0.214	0.002
Seniors	14.15		

Hypothesis 2 – There is a difference between accounting freshmen and accounting seniors in financial self-efficacy.

$$H_0: \sigma_1^2 = \sigma_2^2$$

$$H_1: \sigma_1^2 \neq \sigma_2^2$$

The main research hypothesis states that there is a significant difference between accounting freshmen and accounting seniors in financial self-efficacy. Firstly, Levene's test was employed to determine whether the two populations had equal variances. According to Levene's test, the significance level was 0.007, which was smaller than the confidence level (5%). The null hypothesis (i.e., the two populations have equal variances) was rejected.

$$H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$$

$$H_1: \mu_1 \neq \mu_2$$

However, according to the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test, the mean was considered a measure of central tendency. Therefore, the t-test was used in the next step to analyze the mean hypothesis. The significance level was 0.016, which was lower than the confidence level (5%). Therefore, the null hypothesis (i.e., there is no significant difference between the means of the two populations) was rejected, and Hypothesis 1 (i.e., there is a significant difference between accounting freshmen and accounting seniors in financial self-efficacy) was confirmed. According to the mean, accounting seniors improved their financial self-efficacy as opposed to accounting freshmen.

Table 4. Testing Hypothesis 2

Groups	Mean	F-value (Sig.)	t-value (Sig.)
Freshmen	20.77	0.007	0.016
Seniors	21.20		

Hypothesis 3 – There is a significant difference between critical thinking and financial self-efficacy.

The correlation coefficient for 93 paired data was 0.661, and the significance level was 0.000, which was lower than the confidence level (5%). Therefore, the null hypothesis (i.e., there is no significant correlation between the two variables) was rejected. In

conclusion, there is a significant correlation between these two variables. In other words, this finding indicates that changes in one variable cause changes in another and vice versa.

Discussion

Hypothesis 1 – There is a difference between accounting freshmen and accounting seniors in critical thinking.

According to the results of statistical analyses, there was a significant difference between accounting freshmen and accounting seniors in critical thinking. In other words, accounting seniors outperformed accounting freshmen in critical thinking.

In addition, this finding is consistent with the results reported by (Khoobani, 2017), and (Mildawani et al,2022), who indicated that students would gain experience and improve critical thinking during their education. However, some studies reported that critical thinking would improve less often or remain unchanged during education (Javidi Kalateh Jafarabadi & Abdoli,2010);(Amini & Madani, 2018); (Fathi, 2016); (Mehrabi et al,2011).

In general, there are diverse research findings on critical thinking in university students. Different factors (e.g., educational attainment, gender, and time) can affect the final results. Moreover, critical thinking is an expandable skill that can be improved by practice and experience.

Critical thinking is an important skill in the process of learning and education. It helps students achieve logically reasonable results through analysis, evaluation, and thinking. Regarding the difference between accounting freshmen and accounting seniors in critical thinking, we should know that their levels of critical thinking may vary in their educational conditions(Facione, 2011). Accounting freshmen may face new concepts and topics in the early stages of education and may lack the necessary practical and specialized experience in accounting. Therefore, they may not act competently in the analysis and evaluation of problems. By contrast, accounting seniors can analyze problems better because of passing advanced and practical courses.

Hypothesis 2 – There is a difference between accounting freshmen and accounting seniors in financial self-efficacy.

According to the results of statistical analyses, accounting seniors outperformed accounting freshmen in financial self-efficacy. This finding is consistent with the result reported by(Amini & Madani, 2018) , who indicated that accounting students were financially competent.

Financial self-efficacy is known as an important factor in the success of students in higher education. The students with higher levels of financial self-efficacy will probably be the most competent in higher education. Therefore, improving financial self-efficacy in students should be considered the major goal of training and education programs at schools and universities.

Accounting seniors are more competent than accounting freshmen in financial self-efficacy. Some possible reasons are as follows: further experience and more knowledge about financial problems; access to further references and information; higher levels of responsibility and better financial management; higher levels of concentration on future careers and relevant financial planning. These factors may improve financial self-efficacy in accounting seniors. Nevertheless, every individual may experience different conditions, and general interpretations were inferred from the foregoing factors.

Hypothesis 3 – There is a significant relationship between critical thinking and financial self-efficacy.

According to the research results, there was a significant relationship between critical thinking and financial self-efficacy. Critical thinking means the ability to evaluate information and problems logically, impartially, and analytically. However, financial self-efficacy refers to a person's belief in their ability to manage and control their financial affairs and achieve relevant financial goals.

In this regard, the students with higher levels of critical thinking and financial self-efficacy will probably be more competent in higher education. Critical thinking helps students analyze information logically and impartially and make financial decisions based on such analyses. Furthermore, high levels of financial self-efficacy improve their self-confidence and strong will for financial management and acquisition of financial goals.

Table 5. Hypothesis testing results

Hypothesis	One-Way P-Value (Sig.)	Result at 0.05
Hypothesis 1	0.002	Confirmed
Hypothesis 2	0.016	Confirmed
Hypothesis 3	0.000	Confirmed

Limitations and Future Directions

This study faced the following limitations:

1) Sampling limitation: This study was conducted only on accounting students at a specific university. In other words, the research results cannot be generalized completely to other universities and countries. The special demographics and characteristics of this sample can differ from those of other universities and environments.

2) Research tools limitation: The tools used in this study (e.g., questionnaires) may lack high accuracy and precision. In other words, the research results might be affected by the defect and inaccuracy of these tools. Therefore, they can be interpreted incompletely or inaccurately.

3) Time limitation: This study was conducted only on accounting freshmen and accounting seniors. In other words, behavioral changes in financial self-efficacy and critical thinking cannot be followed up in other years. Thus, the research results may fail to represent long-term changes in these concepts comprehensively.

4) Concept limitation: Critical thinking and financial self-efficacy are complicated and multifaceted concepts with no accurate, uniform definitions. In other words, different studies may use various definitions and concepts. Therefore, the results of different studies are so comparable that generalizing the results to other situations may cause problems.

Nonetheless, these analyses are based on statistical data; thus, their results cannot be generalized to all students. Moreover, there was a correlation between the two variables, and other factors might be involved in their correlation. Therefore, further research should be conducted. Additionally, no studies have yet analyzed the direct relationship between these two variables; therefore, the results cannot be compared with those of other studies.

It is suggested to consider the following topics for future research:

1. Investigating the differences in critical thinking between accounting students and other fields, such as management and economics, and investigating the factors affecting this difference;

2. Examining the relationship between critical thinking and creativity in accounting students;

3. Examining the relationship between financial self-efficacy of first and last year accounting students and their academic performance;

4. Examining the relationship between financial self-efficacy and investment behavior of first and last year accounting students.

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